

Artificial disfluency detection, uh no, disfluency generation for the masses

Tatiana Passali^{a,b,*}, Thanassis Mavropoulos^b, Grigorios Tsoumakas^a,
Georgios Meditskos^a, Stefanos Vrochidis^b

^a School of Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

^b Centre for Research and Technology Hellas, Thessaloniki, Greece

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ABSTRACT

Existing approaches for disfluency detection typically require the existence of large annotated datasets. However, current datasets for this task are limited, suffer from class imbalance, and lack some types of disfluencies that are encountered in real-world scenarios. At the same time, augmentation techniques for disfluency detection are not able to model complex types of disfluencies. This limits such approaches to only performing pre-training since the generated data are not indicative of disfluencies that occur in real scenarios and, as a result, cannot be directly used for training disfluency detection models, as we experimentally demonstrate. This imposes significant constraints on the usefulness of such approaches in practice since real disfluencies still have to be collected in order to train the models. In this work, we propose Large-scale ARTificial Disfluency Generation (LARD), a method for automatically generating artificial disfluencies, and more specifically repairs, from fluent text. Unlike existing augmentation techniques, LARD can simulate all the different and complex types of disfluencies. In addition, it incorporates contextual embeddings into the disfluency generation to produce realistic, context-aware artificial disfluencies. LARD can be used effectively for training disfluency detection models, bypassing the requirement of annotated disfluent data. Our empirical evaluation shows that LARD outperforms existing rule-based augmentation methods and increases the accuracy of existing disfluency detectors. In addition, experiments demonstrate that the proposed method can be effectively used in a low-resource setup.

1. Introduction

Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) technology has recently achieved remarkable progress and is now an integral part of a wide range of intelligent systems, such as general-domain virtual assistants and specialized spoken dialogue systems for healthcare (Latif et al., 2021), migration (Wanner et al., 2021), finance (Wang et al., 2020b) and education (Maxwell-Smith and Foley, 2021). An important challenge when deploying such technology in a real-world application is *speech disfluencies*, such as self-repairs, repetitions, replacements and false starts. These linguistic phenomena are a common feature of spontaneous human speech (Shriberg, 1996). In this paper, we adopt the term “disfluencies” to describe a specific sub-set of disfluency phenomena, following the definition of repairs by Lickley (2015). This subset includes the following disfluency types: repetitions, which are frequent and easier to detect (Zayats

* Corresponding author at: School of Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece.

E-mail addresses: scpassali@csd.auth.gr (T. Passali), mavrathan@iti.gr (T. Mavropoulos), greg@csd.auth.gr (G. Tsoumakas), gmeditsk@csd.auth.gr (G. Meditskos), stefanos@iti.gr (S. Vrochidis).

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et al., 2016), as well as replacements and restarts, which are particularly challenging to detect, highlighting their importance in disfluency detection algorithms (Zwarts et al., 2010; Zwarts and Johnson, 2011; Zayats et al., 2016).

The presence of speech disfluencies can have a negative impact not only on the readability of generated transcripts, but also on the performance in downstream tasks, such as machine translation, question answering, and summarization. For example, Gupta et al. (2021) have shown that the presence of disfluencies in questions can significantly drop the performance of a question-answering model. Existing conversational systems have a varying degree of robustness against speech disfluencies, either handling such phenomena implicitly as part of a downstream task model (Jamshid Lou and Johnson, 2020a), or explicitly as a post-processing step after the ASR component and before a downstream task model (Zayats et al., 2016; Jamshid Lou et al., 2018). Recent literature has shown that the latter approach can significantly improve the performance of ASR systems, bringing them closer to human-level performance (Jamshid Lou and Johnson, 2020a).

Several methods for explicitly handling disfluencies using a dedicated component have been proposed in the literature. The most common is sequence tagging (Ostendorf and Hahn, 2013; Liu et al., 2006; Ferguson et al., 2015), where each token of the input sequence is classified as fluent or disfluent. Deep Learning (DL) has significantly increased the accuracy of sequence tagging in disfluency detection, varying from recurrent neural networks (RNNs) (Hough and Schlangen, 2015; Zayats et al., 2016) and convolutional neural networks (CNNs) (Jamshid Lou et al., 2018) to more recent Transformer-based methods (Dong et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020a; Rocholl et al., 2021).

Despite the great progress of these models, they still suffer from a significant limitation: they heavily rely on the existence of annotated datasets for training and evaluation. However, existing datasets for disfluency detection are limited and do not cover sufficiently all the different types of disfluency that can be encountered in real-world scenarios. For example, Switchboard (Godfrey et al., 1992), the largest and most commonly used dataset for disfluency detection, has a highly imbalanced distribution among the different disfluency classes, with more than 50% of the examples belonging to repetitions (Shriberg, 1996), which is the easiest class of disfluencies according to the literature (Zayats et al., 2016, 2019). Training models on Switchboard can lead to a significant bias towards the repetition class, while evaluating models on it will lead to misleading conclusions with respect to their real-world performance (Passali et al., 2022). An option to remedy this drawback would be to manually annotate datasets with more replacements and restarts. However, this would require enormous human labeling effort and appropriately trained personnel.

Motivated by this observation, we propose an approach for automatically generating highly realistic artificial disfluencies from existing fluent dialogue corpora, without any human supervision. In particular, we propose three distinct algorithms, one for each of the three categories of repair disfluencies (repetition, replacement and restart). The repetition algorithm works by randomly repeating a word or sequences of words within a fluent sentence. In addition, the replacement algorithm works by first extracting possible repair candidates for the replacement using semantic relations such as hypernyms and hyponyms and then selecting the best repair candidate using a BERT-based language model. This way, we ensure that the inserted replacement does not affect the semantic relation between the fluent and the generated disfluent sequence. The proposed replacement algorithm is capable of extracting higher-level semantic information combined with linguistic knowledge in the form of rules. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that leverages contextual embeddings in order to generate realistic synthetic replacements to accommodate the task of disfluency detection. Finally, the restart algorithm breaks apart a fluent sentence at a random position and concatenates it with another fluent sentence. The generated artificial disfluencies can be used directly for training any disfluency detection model, contrary to existing augmentation techniques which are used only for self-supervised pre-training via a denoising objective (Dong et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020a).

Our contributions can be summarized as follows:

- We propose a novel and generic pipeline for automatically generating artificial disfluencies of various types, integrating the capabilities of DL models to extract high-level semantics with prior linguistic knowledge in the form of interpretable rules. The code and data are publicly available.¹
- We provide an empirical evaluation of the proposed method on Switchboard and Disfl-QA (Gupta et al., 2021). Results show that our method can boost the performance of existing models for disfluency detection.
- We conducted a proof-of-concept experiment in a low-resource setup, demonstrating that our method outperforms existing rule-based approaches (Wang et al., 2020a) and can be successfully used with few or no annotated data at all. This is especially important for low-resource languages where disfluent data is scarce.

A preliminary version of this work exists in Passali et al. (2022). Here, we extend it by: (a) incorporating context-aware representations for generating replacements, (b) refining the previously proposed algorithms to improve the quality of the generated disfluencies and filtering non-realistic results, and (c) providing an in-depth experimental evaluation using an additional dataset, both in a regular and in a low-resource setup as well as comparing our method with a competitive rule-based augmentation method.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the structure of disfluencies in human dialogue. Section 3 reviews related literature. Section 4, introduces the proposed method. Section 5 presents and discusses the results of our empirical evaluation. Finally, Section 6, concludes our work and points to interesting future research directions.

2. Disfluencies in human dialogue

This section introduces the structure, as well as the different categories of disfluencies.

¹ <https://github.com/tatianapassali/contextual-artificial-disfluency-generation>.

Table 1
Different types of repair cues as described by Shriberg (1994).

Repair cues	Examples
Filled pauses	um, uh
Editing phrases	oops, no, sorry, wait, I meant to say
Discourse markers	well, actually, okay, you know, I mean

$$\text{Can we meet on } \underbrace{\text{Tuesday}}_{\text{reparandum}} \mid \overbrace{\text{I mean}}^{\text{interregnum}} \underbrace{\text{Friday?}}_{\text{repair}}$$

Fig. 1. An example of a disfluency, where the reparandum, interregnum and repair are illustrated. The vertical bar indicates the interruption point.

2.1. Structure of disfluencies

Shriberg (1994) introduced a standard annotation scheme based on pattern features for identifying disfluencies, called *Pattern Labeling System*. This annotation scheme involves the following fragments: (a) the *reparandum*, (b) the *interruption point*, (c) the *repair*, and, optionally, (d) the *interregnum*, which is located right before the repair. In the rest of this paper, we will refer to this scheme as the *reparandum/interregnum* annotation scheme.

The reparandum indicates the disfluent part of the utterance: the part that is not correct and must be replaced or ignored. Typically, the speaker attempts to rephrase, edit or restate the reparandum. The reparandum is usually short, involving 2 to 3 words. Even though the reparandum is usually considered as a “rough” copy of the repair, it can also be completely irrelevant to the repair.

The interruption point indicates the start of the repair, if no interregnum exists. If an interregnum exists, then the interruption point indicates the start of the interregnum, after which the repair follows. The interruption point does not signify an actual word, it rather serves as a surface-level indicator that marks the moment of speech at which the speaker initiates the correction process. In other words, the interruption point typically occurs right after the last word that is being told before the interruption of speech. However, note that the speaker may have identified the issue earlier than this specific moment in time (Shriberg, 1994).

The interregnum consists of repair cues, such as those shown in Table 1, that are typically used to fill the gap between the disfluent speech and the associated repair. These types of fillers are often removed during the preprocessing phase in many dialogue systems (Dinkar et al., 2022). However, recent research has shown that the use of repair cues can carry specific meaning and can vary among groups (Irvine et al., 2016; MacFarlane et al., 2017; Lawley et al., 2023). As a result, they can potentially provide useful information for disfluency detection algorithms. Interregnums are relatively easy to detect as they are usually fixed phrases, in contrast to reparandums that require a deeper understanding of the complex dialogue flow. For this reason, many methods ignore the interregnum and focus only on the detection of the reparandum and the repair (Zayats et al., 2016, 2019; Jamshid Lou et al., 2018; Bach and Huang, 2019).

We typically meet a repair in a speaker’s utterance either after the presence of an interregnum or directly after the interruption point. The repair is the corrected fragment of speech and is usually different from the reparandum. However, in some cases the repair can be exactly the same as the reparandum or even completely empty.

An example of the aforementioned annotation scheme is described in Fig. 1, where the speaker mistakenly says Tuesday instead of Friday. The disfluent part of this example consists of the words “Tuesday” (reparandum), which is followed by an interregnum (“I mean”), and eventually by the correct choice of day (“Friday”) that makes the particular repair. To simplify the presentation of disfluencies under this scheme, the following notation is typically used to indicate the different parts of disfluencies (Zayats et al., 2016, 2019; Wang et al., 2018):

[reparandum + {interregnum} repair]

In this notation, the brackets (“[” and “]”) are used to indicate the disfluency along with the repair. The interruption point is indicated by the plus symbol (“+”), while the interregnum, if present, is indicated by curly brackets (“{”, “}”).

2.2. Categories of disfluencies

According to the speech repair typology of Shriberg (1994), disfluencies can be categorized into three distinct classes, as described below:

- **Repetitions:** The speaker repeats a word, a phrase or a sequence of words. In repetitions, the reparandum and the corresponding repair are actually the same. This type of disfluency is the most common and is particularly easy to be detected (Zayats et al., 2014, 2019).
- **Replacements:** The speaker replaces the disfluent word(s) or phrase with the fluent one. In replacements, the reparandum is replaced by the repair.

Table 2
Different types of disfluencies annotated based on the reparandum/interregnum scheme.

Type	Example
Repetition	Let's meet [today + today].
Replacement	I want [the blue + {no} the red] one.
Restart	[Why don't you +] I will do it later.

- **Restarts:** The speaker abandons completely the initial utterance and restarts it. This type of disfluency does not actually involve a repair as the speaker begins a completely new utterance.

Different types of speech disfluencies tend to occur in specific locations of utterances and are often associated with particular word types (Goodwin et al., 1980; Clark and Wasow, 1998). For example, repetitions typically appear in function words, such as prepositions and pronouns, rather than in content words like nouns and verbs. Repetitions are most often observed at the beginning of an utterance, though they can appear at any point. Similarly, restarts are more susceptible to occurring in complex utterances and are also typically observed at the start of an utterance (Goodwin et al., 1980). Table 2 presents an example for each of these three categories of disfluencies.

3. Related work

This section reviews related work on disfluency detection. First, we provide an overview of existing models and methods for detecting disfluencies. Then, we present datasets that are used to train the aforementioned models. Finally, we discuss existing augmentation techniques that have been proposed to address the issue of limited data for disfluency detection.

3.1. Disfluency detection models

Several approaches have been proposed for dealing with speech disfluencies in a dialogue. These approaches are divided into four main categories: (a) *sequence tagging*, (b) *translation-based*, (c) *noisy-channel* and (d) (c) *parsing-based* methods. Sequence tagging, which is the most common approach for disfluency detection, classifies each token of the input sequence as fluent or disfluent. This approach includes a wide range of different models varying from Hidden Markov Models (Liu et al., 2006), Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) (Georgila, 2009; Ostendorf and Hahn, 2013), Semi-Markov CRFs (Ferguson et al., 2015), CNNs (Jamshid Lou et al., 2018), RNNs (Zayats et al., 2016), to more recent Transformer-based architectures (Dong et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020a; Chen et al., 2022), and even using an on-device lightweight setup (Rocholl et al., 2021). On the other hand, translation-based methods approach disfluency detection as a sequence-to-sequence problem using encoder–decoder models to generate the corrected sequence without the disfluent fragments by “translating” the disfluent input into a fluent sequence (Saini et al., 2021). Noisy-channel models (Charniak and Johnson, 2001; Johnson and Charniak, 2004) detect disfluencies by computing the similarity between the reparandum and the repair. Parsing-based approaches detect concurrently both the syntactic structure and the disfluencies of the input sequence (Wang et al., 2017; Tran et al., 2019).

These approaches require corresponding annotated training datasets that include both syntactic and disfluency annotations. Even though all these methods have proven effective in disfluency detection, their dependence on large annotated datasets poses significant limitations. Annotating such datasets is often costly and time-consuming which might hinder the usability of these methods on different domains and low-resource languages, where data are scarce.

3.2. Disfluency detection datasets

Switchboard (Godfrey et al., 1992) is the most popular disfluency detection dataset. It is the largest human-annotated dataset with real disfluencies at token-level, based on the reparandum/interregnum scheme. Even though Switchboard contains approximately 190,000 multi-speaker transcriptions of English dialogues on different topics, it has a highly imbalanced class distribution, with only 5.9% of tokens being disfluent. In addition, more than 50% of these disfluent tokens belong to simple repetitions (Charniak and Johnson, 2001), which has been shown to be the most trivial to tackle disfluency type (Charniak and Johnson, 2001).

Disfl-QA (Gupta et al., 2021) is a recent dataset for disfluency detection containing 12,000 human-annotated disfluent questions in English. In contrast to Switchboard, Disfl-QA has a higher number of more complicated disfluencies, such as replacements and restarts. However, it is significantly smaller. Furthermore, because it lacks token-level annotations, it can only be used directly by translation-based models.

Fisher English Training Transcripts (Cieri et al., 2004) contains approximately 1.3 million transcriptions of real dialogues between speakers. Despite being larger than Switchboard, it lacks annotations for the disfluencies it contains and thus cannot be readily used for the task of disfluency detection.

3.3. Data augmentation techniques

Despite the significant progress of DL models, they still rely heavily on the quality and quantity of training data. To address the issue of limited datasets, some early steps towards data augmentation have been made, varying from semi-supervised

techniques (Wang et al., 2018) to self-training approaches (Jamshid Lou and Johnson, 2020b), either by annotating unlabeled datasets, such as Fisher, using existing disfluency detectors trained on Switchboard, or by unsupervised pre-training techniques using artificial data (Dong et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020a). Our work is closer to the latter approach.

Dong et al. (2019) corrupt the input sequence for pre-training by adding noise based on randomly selected input words, while a similar approach is adopted by Yang et al. (2020), where a simple planner-generator model is used to generate and place disfluent text in a fluent sentence. Wang et al. (2020a) generate artificial disfluencies by randomly repeating, inserting, and removing words. As the inserted tokens are randomly selected, the semantic consistency between the created disfluent sentence and the fluent one cannot be guaranteed. The aforementioned approaches rely on simple rules and techniques that are incapable of generating all the different kinds of complex disfluencies that occur in real-world scenarios.

Our work significantly differs from these approaches in several aspects, introducing a novel hybrid generation pipeline that provides both the ability to generate better artificial disfluencies, as well as handling tasks that were not possible before. First, the proposed pipeline is carefully designed to generate and handle all types of repair disfluencies compared to existing approaches that are usually limited to one or two types of disfluencies. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that is capable of handling restarts.

In addition, the proposed method incorporates contextual representations for the generation of synthetic disfluencies, leading to disfluencies that are closer to the ones occurring in natural dialogue flows. More specifically, the proposed method is capable of extracting higher-level semantic information using a BERT-based language model combined with linguistic knowledge in the form of interpretable rules. In this way, the proposed method goes beyond existing approaches that cannot integrate semantic information into the rule-based disfluency generation process, significantly limiting their ability to generate realistic disfluencies, as we also experimentally demonstrate in this paper.

Finally, the proposed method can be used to generate annotated disfluencies for directly training supervised disfluency detectors instead of defining a denoising pre-training objective, which can be computationally costly.

4. Proposed method

In this section, we introduce our improved Large-scale ARTificial Disfluency (LARD) generation method for synthesizing artificial disfluencies from fluent text. The proposed method consists of three algorithms for supporting the corresponding types of disfluencies, namely repetitions, replacements, and restarts.

Given any set of fluent sentences, we can use these algorithms to generate a new set of annotated disfluent sentences containing artificial repetitions, replacements, and restarts at any ratio. Even though all the algorithms can consume the same fluent sentence to generate disfluencies, we use different sub-sets of the fluent set for each algorithm to increase the variation of the generated examples.

4.1. Repetition algorithm

The procedure used for generating artificial repetitions is summarized in Alg. 1. This algorithm works by randomly repeating words or sequences of words based on a given degree ranging from 1 to 3.

For example, given the fluent sequence “Thank you for your help”, we can simulate an artificial disfluent sequence that includes a degree 1 repetition by repeating the word “for” in the third position, or a degree 2 repetition by repeating the sequence of words “thank you”, starting from the first position as follows:

Degree 1: Thank you [for + for] your help

Degree 2: [Thank you + thank you] for your help

During this procedure, we ensure that we select only valid candidates for repetition by excluding tokens that belong to punctuation marks. The repetition algorithm can be used for generating up to degree 3 repetitions, but it can also be easily modified to generate repetitions of higher degrees according to the length of the input sequence.

Algorithm 1 Repetition algorithm

Input: A fluent sequence S_f , the degree of repetition $d_r \in \{1, 2, 3\}$

Output: A disfluent sequence S_d which contains a repetition based on given degree d_r

- 1: **procedure** GENERATE REPETITIONS(S_f, d_r)
 - 2: $l_s \leftarrow \text{length}(S_f)$
 - 3: Choose $\text{random}_{idx} \leftarrow \text{uniform}(0, l_s - d_r)$ matching the condition that the word of the selected index, as well as words up to degree d_r of the subsequent indexes, do not belong to punctuation marks.
 - 4: $S_d \leftarrow$ Repeat the subsequence of tokens in S_f starting from index random_{idx} to degree d_r .
 - 5: **return** S_d
 - 6: **end procedure**
-

4.2. Replacement algorithm

To preserve the semantic consistency between the initial fluent sentence and the generated disfluent one, we introduce a two-step replacement candidate selection process exploiting the semantic relation of the selected candidate with hypernyms and hyponyms. Then, a BERT-based language model is used to select the best candidate from a set of possible candidates. Note that even though the selected candidate is always one word, the replacement algorithm can be used to generate varying degrees of artificial replacements by repeating the fluent part of the utterance prior to the replacement. The replacement algorithm is described in Alg. 2. The steps for generating artificial replacements can be summarized as follows:

1. First, we extract a random word of the initial fluent sentence, whose part-of-speech (POS) is either noun, verb, or adjective, to serve as our *repair candidate*. The POS tagger of Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) (Bird et al., 2009) is used in this step.
2. We detect the hypernym class of the repair candidate, namely its broader semantic category. To this end, NLTK (Bird et al., 2009) can be used.
3. For each hypernym, apart from the original candidate, we extract N hyponyms, namely words that belong to the same broader semantic category. Since hyponyms share common semantic relations, we assume they will be semantically close to the initial repair candidate.
4. For each hyponym, we generate a new sentence based on the initial sentence by substituting the selected repair candidate with the corresponding hyponym. Then, we compute the similarity between all the generated sentences and the original sentence.
5. Instead of randomly selecting a hyponym from the extracted set of hyponyms, we select the best candidate, the one in the sentence with the highest similarity. The best candidate serves as our *reparandum candidate*.
6. To simulate an artificial replacement, the reparandum candidate is placed right before the repair candidate in the initial sentence, to ensure that the fluent sentence will be realistic. Note that the repair candidate is always one word, i.e., the word at which the repair ends, but the reparandum candidate can vary from 1 to 4 words according to the extracted hyponym.
7. Optionally, we can add a repair cue (interregnum) between the replacement and the repair candidate. We create a fixed list of repair cues with some variations of words and phrases from Table 1. Note that filled pauses, such as um and uh, are not included in this list as these types of disfluencies are typically removed automatically from recent ASR systems.

Algorithm 2 Replacement algorithm

Input: A fluent sequence S_f , part-of-speech $s_{pos} \in \{\text{noun, verb, adjective}\}$, the range of hyponyms N , a boolean variable cue ,

Output: A disfluent sequence S_d which contains a replacement based on the part-of-speech s_{pos}

```

1: procedure CREATE REPLACEMENT( $S_f, s_{pos}, N, cue$ )
2:   while there is  $s_{pos}$  in  $S_f$  do
3:      $W_{pos} \leftarrow$  a list with all of the available words of the sequence  $S_f$  that belong to the selected input part-of-speech  $s_{pos}$ 
4:     Select randomly one of the available words from  $W_{pos}$  to serve as repair candidate
5:     Detect the hypernym of the repair candidate. If there are more than one hypernym extract all the possible hypernyms.
6:     Extract  $N$  hyponyms for each hypernym, excluding the repair candidate.
7:      $\{S\} \leftarrow N$  new sequences based on  $S_f$  with the substitution of the repair candidate with the corresponding hyponym in
        $S_f$ 
8:     Compute the similarity between all the sentences and the  $S_f$  and select as reparandum candidate the hyponym whose
       sentence has the highest similarity.
9:      $d_r \leftarrow \text{uniform}(0, 3)$ 
10:    Repeat  $d_r$  tokens before the replacement candidate
11:    Place the reparandum candidate
12:    if  $cue == \text{True}$  then randomly select a repair cue from list and place it after the reparandum candidate.
13:    end if
14:    Continue the rest of  $S_f$ .
15:    return  $S_d$ 
16:  end while
17: end procedure

```

To compute the similarity between each generated sentence with the initial sentence, we first employ a BERT-based model to extract sentence embeddings SE , by mean-pooling all the token embeddings of the given sentence as follows:

$$SE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} TE(i), \quad (1)$$

where $TE(i)$ represents the token embedding of the i th token, while n denotes the number of tokens in the given sentence.

The final reparandum candidate r is selected as follows:

$$r = \max_{i \in T} \{sim(SE_s, SE_i)\}, \quad (2)$$

where T represents the set of the hyponym-generated sentences, SE_s and SE_i denote the sentence embeddings of the initial sentence s and the generated sentence with the hyponym i of the set T respectively, while sim denotes the cosine similarity between two vectors \mathbf{x}_y and \mathbf{x}_z , computed as follows:

$$sim(\mathbf{x}_y, \mathbf{x}_z) = \frac{\mathbf{x}_y \cdot \mathbf{x}_z}{\|\mathbf{x}_y\| \|\mathbf{x}_z\|}. \quad (3)$$

The replacement algorithm can be used to generate varying degrees of replacements. These can range from simple replacements involving only one word to more complicated n -word replacements ($n > 1$) involving multiple words in both reparandum and repair. For the latter, we repeat a sequence of words before the reparandum candidate. We limit this sequence length to 3 words in order to ensure that the generated sentences will be coherent and realistic.

For example, given fluent sequence “*I would like to eat pancakes for breakfast*”, we can simulate an artificial noun-replacement by selecting the word “pancakes”, whose POS is a noun, as our repair candidate. We extract its hypernym class, namely “cake”. Some possible hyponyms for the word “cake” are “gingerbread”, “cheesecake”, “doughnut”, “honey cake”, “brownie” etc. Then, we generate all the possible sentence candidates, like “*I would like to eat gingerbread for breakfast*” and “*I would like to eat cheesecake for breakfast*”, and compute their similarity with the initial fluent sentence. The best candidate e.g., “cheesecake”, is the one belonging to the sentence with the highest similarity. Note that we can also use a repair cue from the fixed list of repair cues e.g., “no wait”. Finally, we can generate a simple artificial disfluent sequence by replacing the reparandum candidate “cheesecake” with the repair candidate “pancakes” or a three-word replacement by also repeating the sub-sequence of words “to eat”, starting from the fourth position as follows:

One-word: I would like to eat [cheesecake + {no} pancakes] for breakfast

Three-word: I would like [to eat cheesecake + {no} to eat pancakes] for breakfast

The same process can be used to generate an artificial verb replacement. For example, given a fluent sequence “*I prefer tea instead of coffee*”, we can simulate an artificial verb replacement by selecting the verb “prefer” as our repair candidate, whose hypernym class is “like”. Some possible hyponyms for the word “like” are “enjoy”, “choose”, “opt for”, “pick” etc. Then, a potential artificial two-word replacement without a repair cue starting from the first position would be as follows:

[I choose + I prefer] tea instead of coffee.

Finally, given a fluent sequence “*She is such a cheerful person.*”, we can generate an artificial adjective replacement as follows. First, we select the adjective “cheerful” as our repair candidate, whose hypernym class is the word “happy”. Some possible hyponyms for the word “happy” are “joyful”, “pleased”, “delighted” etc. Then, a possible artificial one-word adjective replacement without a repair cue would be as follows:

She is such a [joyful + cheerful] person.

Following this procedure, we can simulate six different sub-classes of replacements: noun replacement with and without repair cue, verb replacement with and without repair cue and adjective replacement with and without repair cue.

Note that in this work, we use hypernyms and hyponyms for the generation of the reparandum candidate, however the algorithm can be trivially adjusted to also work with other types of relationships, such as synonyms (e.g., I like, uh, love playing the piano), antonyms (e.g., I need a different, uhm no, same size), or meronyms (e.g., it has three sections, uh, shelves for organizing books) as well as morpho-syntactic level relations (e.g., she go, uh, she went to the store yesterday).

4.3. Restart algorithm

Contrary to the repetition and replacement algorithm, this algorithm assumes the existence of a set of two or more fluent sentences. The steps for generating artificial restarts are summarized in Alg. 3. First, we extract two different sentences from a given fluent set. Note that the length of the first sentence should be at least 4 tokens in order to be able to use this sentence for generating a restart. The same limitation applies to the second sentence in order to ensure that meaningful synthetic samples will be generated. Then, we split the first sentence at a random position, and we concatenate this broken sentence with the second fluent one.

For example, given two fluent sequences “*I would like to buy a new dress*” and “*Can we meet on Tuesday?*”, we can simulate a disfluent sentence with an artificial restart by splitting the first sentence in the second position and concatenating it with the second sentence as follows:

[I would +] can we meet on Tuesday?

As discussed in Section 2, this type of disfluency does not involve a repair as the speaker abandons the previous sentence and restarts with a new one.

During this procedure, it is possible to accidentally generate a fluent sentence instead of a disfluent one. This might happen when the connection point for the given sentences happens to belong to a connective word or phrase. As connective words are typically used to link one sentence with another, their presence might result in a fluent and coherent sentence. To alleviate this issue, we create a list of possible connectives according to the different types that can occur in a real dialogue flow, e.g. additive (and, also etc.), causal (because, if, since etc.), adversative (but, however, etc.), and temporal (after, before, etc.). Then, while concatenating the two sentences, we check for the presence of connective words and filter such sentences to avoid the generation of fluent examples. Also, we ensure that the end of the first broken sentence is not the same as the beginning of the second sentence to avoid unintentionally generating a repetition instead of a restart.

Algorithm 3 Restart algorithm

Input: Two fluent sequences S_{f1} and S_{f2} , with $S_{f1} \neq S_{f2}$ and $\text{length}(S_{f1}) > 4$, $\text{length}(S_{f2}) > 4$

Output: A disfluent sequence S_d

```

1: procedure CREATE_RESTARTS( $S_{f1}$ ,  $S_{f2}$ )
2:    $S'_{f1} \leftarrow S_{f1}$  broken in a random position.
3:   while  $S'_{f1} \neq$  beginning of  $S_{f2}$  do
4:     Check for connective words at the end of  $S'_{f1}$  or at the beginning of  $S_{f2}$ 
5:     if no connective words detected then
6:        $S_d \leftarrow \text{join}(S'_{f1}, S_{f2})$ 
7:       return  $S_d$ 
8:     else
9:       Select another sequence  $S_{f2}$ 
10:    end if
11:  end while
12: end procedure

```

Table 3
Dataset statistics. All numbers are reported in sentences.

Dataset	Train	Validation	Test
Switchboard	165,463	14,026	7406
Disfl-QA (original)	7182	1000	3643
Disfl-QA (sequence tagging)	5537	780	2460

5. Empirical evaluation

In this section, we introduce the training and evaluation details of our experimental setup, as well as present and discuss the results of our empirical evaluation.

5.1. Experimental setup

We conduct experiments with sequence tagging and translation-based approaches. For sequence tagging, we use the pre-trained BERT-base uncased model, which consists of 12 encoder layers with 12 attention heads. For the translation-based approach, we use the pre-trained T5-base model (Raffel et al., 2020), which consists of 12 encoder and decoder layers with 12 attention heads as well. For the generation process of the reparandum candidate, we use NLTK (Bird et al., 2009) which provides hypernyms and hyponyms for verbs and nouns. In addition, for extracting vector representations when generating artificial replacements, we use the multi-qa-distilbert-cos-v1 model (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019), a lightweight distilBERT-based model fine-tuned appropriately for the task of semantic search.

We fine-tune all the models for 10 epochs with learning rate $2e-5$ and batch size 16. We do not perform extensive hyperparameter search as this lies beyond the scope of this paper. Further fine-tuning or more extensive hyperparameter tuning could lead to improved models. All the conducted experiments were performed using the Hugging Face library (Wolf et al., 2020).

We train and evaluate our disfluency models on Switchboard and Disfl-QA. Switchboard provides token-level annotations and can be easily used for both sequence-tagging and translation-based approaches. For sequence tagging, we classify each token as fluent or disfluent. More specifically, we classify as disfluent all the tokens that are located before the repair inside the disfluent fragment. Similarly, we classify as fluent all the tokens after the interruption point inside the disfluent fragment as well as all the tokens located outside the disfluent fragment. We use the established train/validation/test split for training and evaluation (Charniak and Johnson, 2001). Following Rocholl et al. (2021), we also discard partial words and words that belong to interregnum such as “uh”, “um”, etc. because they are trivially detected by recent ASR systems.

Disfl-QA provides only raw disfluent sentences accompanied with their respective target fluent versions. Therefore, it can only be used with translation-based models. We adapt this dataset for sequence tagging by mapping one-to-one annotations between the fluent and disfluent sentences. Examples where fluent sentences are not sub-sentences of the disfluent ones are discarded. Some statistics for both datasets are shown in Table 3.

For all the sequence tagging models, we report token-based recall, precision and F-measure. For translation-based models, we report BLEU score (Papineni et al., 2002).

5.2. Results

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method, we conduct two different types of experiments, examining: (a) the effect of the proposed method in a low resource setup when no or few data are available, and (b) the compatibility of the generated artificial disfluencies with real data.

Table 4

Results on sequence-tagging models fine-tuned on limited samples of both Switchboard and Disfl-QA dataset, with or without artificial generated disfluencies. Average token-based f-measure (F1) (%) is reported.

Switchboard	Switchboard				Disfl-QA			
	0 real	1K real	2K real	5K real	0 real	100 real	200 real	500 real
Real data	–	82.41	87.61	87.60	–	78.09	84.48	90.41
Rule-based (Wang et al., 2020a)	81.97	75.98	79.07	84.27	61.32	78.15	83.05	89.11
LARD (Ours)	84.84	86.76	87.85	89.71	84.23	87.16	88.75	91.63

5.2.1. Low-resource setting

In this experiment, we simulate a low-resource setting by keeping only a few samples from each dataset according to their initial size. We report both the results when using only low-resource real data and when combining artificial samples with real data. In order to provide a more complete evaluation, we have modified an existing rule-based approach (Wang et al., 2020a) to support the generation of artificial data for training a supervised machine learning model. The rule-based method generates artificial repetitions by randomly repeating up to six subsequent tokens of the given fluent sentence, while the artificial replacements are generated by randomly selecting and inserting an n-gram from the training corpus into the fluent sentence. Note that this method is limited to generating only artificial repetitions and replacements using a simple heuristic and lacks the ability to generate artificial restarts. On the other hand, our LARD method can generate all the different types of disfluencies, including restarts, while also employing contextual models for preserving semantic consistency. A sequence-tagging model is employed for all the experiments. All the models were evaluated on the original test sets of Switchboard and Disfl-QA.

More specifically, our evaluation includes the following setups:

- **0 real samples (Switchboard).** We use the rule-based (Wang et al., 2020a) and the LARD method to generate different types of artificial disfluencies on the fluent set of Switchboard (82,315 fluent sentences). To get closer to the original distribution of the Switchboard test set (~22% disfluent sentences), we generate 31,034 examples of artificial disfluencies, consisting of 17,047 repetitions and 13,987 replacements for both methods (LARD and rule-based). We do not include any artificial restarts because, as demonstrated later in this section, the nature of Switchboard dialogues can negatively affect the model’s performance when the restart algorithm is used. We fine-tune the model on 82,315 fluent examples of Switchboard combined with the 31,034 generated artificial disfluencies, leading to an artificial training set of 113,349 examples. We do not include any real disfluency from the original dataset.
- **0 real samples (Disfl-QA).** We use the 5537 target fluent sentences of Disfl-QA to generate different types of artificial disfluencies. Similar to Switchboard, we maintain the original distribution of disfluencies in the Disfl-QA dataset (more than 65% replacements and 30% restarts). After applying LARD, we obtain 3600 artificial replacements and 1937 artificial restarts. We do not include artificial repetitions since repetitions are not included in the original training set of Disfl-QA. For the rule-based method, we include only artificial replacements (5537) since this method is not capable of generating artificial restarts. We do not include any real disfluency from the original datasets.
- **1K/2K/5K real samples (Switchboard).** We sample 1000 (841 fluent and 169 disfluent), 2000 (1682 fluent and 318 disfluent), and 5000 (4217 fluent and 783 disfluent) examples from the original Switchboard training dataset, and we fine-tune the model on the corresponding subset. We keep the original distribution of the training data regarding the number of repetitions, replacements, and restarts. We combine these samples with the corresponding artificial disfluencies as generated by the rule-based baseline and our LARD method, respectively.
- **100/200/500 real samples (Disfl-QA).** We sample 100, 200 and 500 disfluent examples from the original Disfl-QA training and we fine-tune the model on the corresponding subset. Since Disfl-QA is a significantly smaller dataset than Switchboard, we reduce the samples of real examples by an order of magnitude. Note that Disfl-QA contains only the original disfluent examples. We combine these samples with the corresponding artificial disfluencies as generated by the rule-based baseline and our LARD method, respectively.

Results in Table 4 demonstrate that even when no real disfluent data are used, the LARD method can achieve an adequate performance of more than 84% in terms of F1 for both datasets, only with artificial disfluencies. This finding is promising, as it suggests that the proposed method can be successfully used for low-resource languages, where annotated datasets for disfluency detection do not typically exist. In addition, the LARD method can achieve better performance on the Switchboard dataset when only artificial disfluencies are used compared to the model fine-tuned with 1000 samples of real data, which achieves 82.41% in terms of F1. The same conclusions can be drawn for the Disfl-QA dataset, where better performance is achieved with only artificial disfluencies compared to the model fine-tuned with 100 disfluent samples with only 78.09% F1. On the other hand, the rule-based method fails to compete with the LARD method with only 61.32% and 81.97% in terms of F1 for Disfl-QA and Switchboard, respectively, when only artificial data are employed. In addition, the rule-based method exhibits a significant drop when combined with any setting of real data, which further highlights its limited ability to capture the variation of real data.

Additional gains are observed when the artificial data of the LARD method are combined with samples of real data. We can notice that all the models fine-tuned with combined data outperform all the models that are fine-tuned only with the corresponding samples of real data in terms of F1 for both datasets. Furthermore, the best performance for the Switchboard dataset is achieved, when 5000 samples are combined with artificial disfluent data, with an increase of more than 6 points in terms of precision (98.08% compared

Table 5

Results on sequence-tagging and translation-based models fine-tuned on Disfl-QA with inserted artificial repetitions (rep.), replacements (repl.) and restarts (res.).

	Sequence tagging			Translation-based
	Prec	Rec	F1	BLEU
original	96.07	96.02	96.04	94.95
original + rep.	96.38	96.24	96.31	94.90
original + repl.	96.25	96.10	96.18	94.96
original + rest.	96.54	96.41	96.69	94.91
original + all	96.32	96.13	96.22	95.10

Table 6

Results on sequence-tagging and translation-based models fine-tuned on Switchboard with inserted artificial repetitions (rep.), replacements (repl.) and restarts (res.).

	Sequence tagging			Translation-based
	Prec	Rec	F1	BLEU
original	96.45	91.63	93.89	91.18
original + rep.	96.41	92.77	94.50	91.24
original + repl.	96.11	92.31	94.12	91.17
original + rest.	92.32	92.28	92.30	90.50
original + rep. + repl.	96.57	92.05	94.18	91.21

to 91.23%) and more than two points in terms of F1 (89.71% compared to 87.60%). Similarly, we obtain the best performance for the Disfl-QA dataset, when 500 samples are inserted into artificial disfluent data of the LARD method, with an increase of more than 5 points in terms of precision (92.34% compared to 86.64%) and more than 3 points in terms of F1 (91.63% compared to 78.09%). In all cases, a performance increase is noticed, which further demonstrates the capability of the proposed method to achieve strong performance with no or only a few annotated data in contrast to simpler rule-based approaches.

5.2.2. Artificial disfluencies with real disfluent data

In many cases, the insertion of artificial disfluencies directly into real disfluent data for training can lead to a performance decrease due to distribution shifts between the real and artificial data (Dong et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2020). However, in this experiment, we demonstrate that the proposed method does not alter the distribution of real data, by generating realistic disfluencies, which increases the accuracy of existing models. In particular, we investigate the effect of artificial disfluencies when inserted directly into the full Switchboard and Disfl-QA training sets. We extract all the fluent sentences of both datasets and we generate all the different types of artificial disfluencies, namely repetitions, replacements and restarts. We insert 3000 and 10,000 artificial repetitions, replacements and restarts for Disfl-QA and Switchboard, respectively. Then, we fine-tune both sequence tagging and translation-based models on the original training datasets with different types of inserted disfluencies. Results of inserted repetitions, replacements, and restarts on the Disfl-QA and Switchboard dataset are shown in Tables 5 and 6, respectively. All the models were evaluated on the original test set of Disfl-QA and Switchboard, respectively.

Results in Table 5 indicate that when synthetic data of any type are inserted, the performance of all the sequence tagging models is increased, contrary to when no synthetic data is used. Similar results are observed for the majority of the translation-based models, where inserted replacements and restarts lead to an increased performance as well. The highest accuracy is achieved when artificial restarts are inserted for the sequence tagging model with 96.69% compared to 96.04% in terms of F1 and when both artificial replacements and restarts are inserted for the translation-based model with 95.10% compared to 94.95% in terms of BLEU score. This finding suggests that the generated artificial disfluencies can be effectively combined with existing datasets that contain real disfluencies without altering their distributions.

Similar results are obtained on the Switchboard dataset as shown in Table 6, where the majority of fine-tuned models with inserted disfluencies achieve an increased accuracy. However, contrary to Disfl-QA, we noticed a slight drop in performance when artificial restarts are inserted into the original dataset. This can be attributed to the nature of Switchboard examples, which are typically incomplete sentences. In some cases, this can be tricky for the restart algorithm, leading to misclassified fluent sentences. Therefore, even though the drop in performance is not significant, artificial restarts should be generated with caution. Additionally, the best performance is obtained when both repetitions and replacements are inserted with 94.18% in terms of F1 and 92.05% in terms of recall, compared to the 93.89% and 91.63% of the model fine-tuned on the original dataset. For the translation-based model, we achieve the best accuracy when only artificial repetitions are inserted with 91.24% compared to 91.18% in terms of BLEU score. Since translation-based is a more challenging task, we expect a slighter increase in contrary to the sequence tagging task. In addition, the combination of both repetitions and replacement still increases the accuracy of the original model with 91.21% compared to 91.18% BLEU score.

6. Conclusions and future work

Disfluency detection is an important task for various downstream applications, such as dialogue systems, machine translation, question answering, and summarization. However, existing disfluency detectors face significant limitations since they heavily rely on large annotated datasets which are often sparse and suffer from class imbalance. Existing augmentation techniques for this task also fall short in modeling complex disfluencies limiting their usefulness only to pre-training. In this work, we proposed LARD, a method for automatically generating artificial disfluencies, integrating the capabilities of DL models with prior linguistic knowledge in the form of rules. The proposed method consists of three different algorithms for handling three different types of repair disfluencies: repetitions, replacements, and restarts. LARD can be directly used without any labeled data to successfully train disfluency detection models. Our empirical evaluation showed the effectiveness of the proposed method in a low-resource setup when no or few annotated data are available. More specifically, in a low-resource setup, LARD achieves a BLEU score of ~90%, surpassing the ~84% obtained by existing augmentation methods, on the Switchboard dataset. Similarly, on the Disfl-QA dataset, LARD achieves a BLEU score of ~92%, outperforming the ~89% achieved by rule-based approaches. At the same time, when no annotated data are available, LARD still maintains strong performance, achieving BLEU scores of ~85% on the Switchboard and ~84% on the Disfl-QA dataset, compared to ~82% and ~61%, respectively, of existing augmentation methods. In addition, our analysis confirmed that LARD can generate realistic disfluencies that do not alter the distribution of data that contain real disfluencies.

Future work could focus on refining the proposed algorithms. For the repetition algorithm, efforts could be directed towards targeting specific locations in the utterance where repetitions are most likely to occur. For the replacement algorithm, additional types of semantic relationships besides hypernyms and hyponyms could be explored for the generation of the reparandum candidate. Similarly, the restart algorithm could benefit from incorporating contextual similarity to produce more coherent restarts. Finally, future research could examine the effect of the proposed method on generating more than one disfluency per sentence.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tatiana Passali: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Thanassis Mavropoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Grigorios Tsoumakas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Georgios Meditskos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Stefanos Vrochidis:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The research data and code can be accessed at <https://github.com/tatianapassali/contextual-artificial-disfluency-generation>.

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